

1 **Genes that regulate aging and cachexia (wasting) in humans.**

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6 1. Genes with suspected functions in aging in humans.

7 a. The genes studied here are important for osteoclast or osteoclast biology, development of the
8 skeletal system, or calcium metabolism.

9 Genes with described functions in the aging process whose specific activities, relevance across tissues
10 and broader importance in the context of other systems thought to function in the aging process, like
11 molecules encoded by the Mboat family (e.g., Mboat7) and growth factors encoded by the GDF family
12 (e.g., GDF15) is not yet completely understood.

- 13 I. Stannocalcin
- 14 II. Osteomodulin
- 15 III. Osteoprogerin
- 16 IV. Osteoglycin
- 17 V. Ostf1
- 18 VI. Cdh11
- 19 VII. Ostm1
- 20 VIII. Postn

21 We performed discovery of genes important for using transcriptomic methods to identify OGN and OMD
22 co-regulated genes.

- 23 1. Cdh11
- 24 2. Islr2
- 25 3. Mgp
- 26 4. Lrrc17
- 27 5. Smoc2
- 28 6. Igf1
- 7. Fgf7
- 8. Cxcl12
- 9. Pdgfrl
- 10. Emcn
- 11. Sparcl1
- 12. C7
- 13. Fkbp7
- 14. Flrt2
- 15. Fmod
- 16. Pcolce2
- 17. Plac9
- 18. Abca6
- 19. Abca9

1 2. Genes important for cachexia in humans with cancer.

2 We measured total transcription in visceral adipose tissue and subcutaneous adipose tissue, comparing
3 total gene expression between adipose tissues obtained from humans with cancer to identify soluble
4 factors and other genes that regulate cachexia in humans with cancer.

5 Cachexia is an end-stage wasting process and is best described by dystrophy or degeneration of the
6 muscles, but with an implicit relationship to death and the aging process in humans resulting from the
7 chronologic emergence of the process in patients affected (metastatic end-stage cancer).

8 GSE186466

9 Silenced

- 10 a. Crndc
- 11 b. Tbx15
- 12 c. Hoxc9
- 13 d. Hoxc6
- 14 e. Hoxc8
- 15 f. Irx1
- 16 g. Irx2
- 17 h. Irx3
- 18 i. Smoc1
- 19 j. Fgfr2
- 20 k. Sim1
- 21 l. Bmp5
- 22 m. Cxcl14

23 Activated

- 24 a. Tcf21
- 25 b. Gdf15
- 26 c. Lif
- 27 d. Ccr2
- 28 e. Cxcl16
- f. Prr16
- g. Tnfrsf10
- h. Grem1
- i. Tff3
- j. Ror2
- k. Ptgds
- l. Ccl21
- m. Sfrp2
- n. Mmrn1
- o. Pamr1
- p. Wnt5a
- q. Il17rd
- r. Nr2f1
- s. Plat
- t. Prox
- u. Adamtsl3
- v. Inmt

w. Rgs2

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- x. Clec12a
- y. Ulk4p2

We also measured total transcription within a defined cancer type, PDAC, comparing to tissue from healthy control individuals.

GSE133979

Control subcutaneous adipose tissue vs
PDAC cachexia subcutaneous adipose tissue

See also: GSE174128

Silenced

1. Syvn1
2. Ch25h
3. Aplnr
4. Clec4g
5. Thy1
- 6.

Activated

1. Tbcd
2. Gatad1
3. Rpl32
4. Hebp2
5. Dmc1
6. Poli
7. Mrnip
8. Pcyox1l
9. Dhrc7
10. Mrps9
11. Map1lc3
12. CSKMT
13. Tamm41
14. Fau
15. Khdc4
16. Vars2
17. Pdpf

1 3. An Mboat7 centered network.

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3 We recently identified, using transcriptome data from young and aged humans, Mboat7 as a molecule of
4 interest based on its suspected function in control of processes governing aging in humans. The precise
5 mechanisms and pathways Mboat7 regulates remain unknown.

6 We used transcriptomic co-regulation methods to identify Mboat7 interactants and obtain evidence
7 supporting a putative function in aging.

- 8 1. Spock family genes (Spock1-3)
- 9 2. Sparc
- 10 3. Sirtuin 7
- 11 4. Mboat2
- 12 5. Cmip
- 13 6. Fibp
- 14 7. Gas2l1
- 15 8. Elfn3
- 16 9. Lrtn1 and Lrtn2
- 17 10. Hpcal4: hippocalcin
- 18 11. Tfe3
- 19 12. Abca2
- 20 13. Pdp1
- 21 14. Ly6h
- 22 15. Emc10
- 23 16. Ifne

24 5. A GDF15 centered network.

25 We recently identified, using transcriptome data from young and aged humans, GDF15 as a molecule of
26 interest based on its suspected function in control of processes governing aging in humans. The precise
27 mechanisms and pathways GDF15 regulates remain unknown.

28 We used transcriptomic co-regulation methods to identify GDF15 interactants and obtain evidence
supporting a putative function in aging.

1. Gfpt1
2. P4ha2 and p4hb
3. FNDC3b
4. Itgb5
5. Cd151
6. Spr
7. Lif

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8. Vegfa
 9. Tgif1
 10. Tnfrsf10b
 11. Idh1
 12. Rpn2
 13. FLJ35776
 14. C8prf4
 15. Tfpi
 16. Ifitm3
 17. Met
 18. Fnbp1l (formin binding)
 19. Farp1
 20. Pvr12
 21. Phlda1 and Phlda2
 22. Ahr
 23. Il8
 24. Prss23
 25. Tnfrsf21
 26. Coq10b